

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AMOAH-KWAKYE****FIRST NAME: SIKA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 5%

The author used the following software: MS Word 365 (on Windows 10)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Academic Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7-14)
2. The Use of Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. American versus British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25-27)
4. Avoiding Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. Use of Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 59-62)
6. Style Guides (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024a, 40-46)
7. The Chicago Manual Style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 43-56)

FUNDAMENTALS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is the signature of every scholar. Therefore, I am thrilled to commence my Ph.D. journey with academic writing to help me grasp the rudiments of writing academic papers, publishing, and communicating with intellectuals and scholars around the globe.

The overall goal of ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack Period One (1) is to expose students to the fundamentals of academic writing and to have a glimpse of lecturers' review and marking of response papers. The major themes covered in the Period One material included academic paper writing, rules of thumb for producing effective papers, referencing, and avoiding plagiarism, appropriate and inappropriate use of punctuation with examples, the use of Latin expressions and abbreviations, British versus American English, and a sampled marked response paper to give students, a glimpse of how lecturers mark response papers.

It is the convention at Euclid University that academic courses are broken down into periods for students to study and write a response paper after each period. Hence, this

response paper summarizes and critically examines eight (8) key concepts, including essay writing, punctuation, British versus American English, avoiding plagiarism, writing style guides, the Chicago writing style, and the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions in the ACA-401/ACA-401D Course Pack, Period One.

2) ESSAY WRITING

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma, academic writings are factual writings that are authored as a result of academic work. Some common examples of academic writing are research findings published in books, journals, and periodicals, unpublished works, thesis conference proceedings, monographs, conference papers thesis, dissertations, and many others. The main objective of academic writing is to communicate ideas from evidence-based research (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7).

My interaction with the course material has shown that academic writings are not authored in isolation and should always be situated in the context of what others have done to help advance new knowledge. Furthermore, Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024,), opine that there is no straight jacket or hard and fast rule for writing academic papers. However, they emphasized the need for one to follow some basic steps, such as researching the subject area while keeping the question to be answered in mind, organizing ideas before producing the first draft (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 9-11). I concur with the authors' advice because producing a well-organized paper without a blueprint or a guide will be challenging.

Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024a) also advised that for effective writing, one must start early, avoid procrastination, produce a draft, and set the draft aside days before reviewing or editing the work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11). These tips are spot-on and very useful. From my personal experience, I have found that whenever I rush to complete an academic paper, I produce an incoherent essay with many avoidable mistakes. Hence, starting early, setting aside a draft, and editing later to allow fresh ideas to be incorporated helps me to write an excellent academic paper.

Again, my interaction with the learning pack taught me to develop the body of an academic paper as a first step to guide the writing of the introduction and the concluding part (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 11). Even though I have been writing academic papers, this tip is new. I always write papers following the order of introduction, body, and conclusion. I see the reason for writing the introduction after the body. I produced this paper's body before the introduction and conclusion and realized it was more effective.

Another major surprise I found in the material is to use active voice as much as possible in academic writing to allow for clarity (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 13). This EUCLID (2024) advice came to me as a surprise. This is because I have always equated passive voice to formality. Thus, I must be ready to unlearn and relearn in this academic journey at any time.

Lastly, the authors made it explicit that all academic essays must be referenced to avoid plagiarism and its untoward consequences (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 14, 34). Euclid recommends that the Turabian style be used, or it will accept any referencing style on the caveat that there is consistency. However, upon further reflection, I think it would be good and effective if EUCLID accepted only one style to allow consistency in all papers submitted to the institution, as is done in other schools to avoid confusion.

3) THE USE OF PUNCTUATION

The Period 1 Coursepack content on punctuation marks was very refreshing as I had forgotten about the existence and use of those punctuations. The punctuations introduced include apostrophes, exclamation marks, brackets, period/ full stops, hyphens, bullet points, commas, question marks, and quotation marks, with examples of accurate and wrongful uses of punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23). This content was beneficial to me as I quickly identified with the examples, and it helped close the knowledge gap regarding the use of punctuation.

Furthermore, according to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024), punctuations should be used sparingly as needed "... while retaining the meaning of a sentence" as a general rule (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16). This cautionary statement drew my attention to reflect on punctuation use in general. I realized that one needs to be careful when using punctuation, as it can change the intended meaning of a sentence. For example, "its" and "it's" have different meanings. Whereas "its" is a possessive pronoun, "it's" is a contracted form of "it is." Therefore, upon careful reflection on the course content on punctuation, I concluded that disregarding the correct use of punctuation marks can lead to poorly written academic papers.

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024), American English influence has grown steadily since World War II. Due to several factors, such as the size of the American population, the economy, mass media influence, and the size of the publishing industry, among others. The authors assert that British and American English are variants of World English with similarities and differences, albeit more "similar than different" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25-28).

Furthermore, the course pack attributed some of the root causes of the differences between American and British English to words pronounced differently but spelled the same, different spelling but the same pronunciation, exact words but additional meanings, grammar, syntax, punctuations, and dates. Until I began this course, I did not know that differences such as these existed between British and American English beyond different spelling and similar meanings. Upon carefully reflecting on the education, I received from Ghana (a former British colony), I realized that I was exposed to British English during my early years of education. However, in succeeding years, American spellings and

pronunciations have increasingly become part of my vocabulary and grammar, confirming the assertion by the authors that American English is steadily influencing world English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25).

Interestingly, amid the increasing adulteration of my British English with American English, I did not make a conscious effort to stick to British or American English in writing since I took both to be the same English or saw them to be similar rather than different just as the authors observed (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 25). However, upon reflection on the course material, I now see the need to stick to any of them and maintain consistency when writing academic papers.

5) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024), plagiarism is “when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35). I concur with the authors that plagiarism is unfair, unethical and a serious academic offense. Culprits must suffer the consequences of plagiarism, such as paper cancellation, dismissal, or loss of marks, and must be prosecuted. The authors further suggested that to avoid plagiarism, quotations and paraphrases must be cited in-text and included in the list of references or bibliography at the end of the work (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35).

Even though I have always known the importance of citation in academic writing and have been using it, this course material has helped me to identify gaps in what I already knew. For instance, I did not know that in-text citations of quotations that are more than four sentences should not be put in quotation marks and that they should be indented instead (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35). Reflecting on these points and others in the period one (1) course pack, it has dawned on me that incorrect use of punctuation could lead to wrong in-text citations that could lead to plagiarism. Thus, I can see that the various contents of the course pack are interlinked. Therefore, I need not study the various content in isolation or in a stand-alone fashion to be an excellent academic writer. However, I must appreciate the linkages between the various content and bring them together in my writing.

Additionally, I think it is unethical, disingenuous, and criminal for me to use somebody’s work without giving him credit. I believe that correctly citing somebody’s work shows scholarship and respect for fellow authors.

6) STYLE GUIDE

In my opinion, a style guide means different things to different writers. In simple terms, a style guide is how a writer or a scholar writes to conform to a specific writing guide consistently. From the course material, I think what constitutes a style guide is fuzzy, as different people see it differently. This is partly because many style guides have no singular source of authority. This notwithstanding, an organization or a writer committing to a style guide ensures consistency, saves time, and makes the writing unique. Hence, the

development and use of personalized documented guidelines by technical writers, journalists, institutions, and companies (e.g., Euclid University, the Economist, the British Broadcasting Corporation) for writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 42).

While technical writers, journalists, and businesses see the need for style guides for their writing, creative writers disregard style guides and see them as an inborn attribute of a good writer. Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024), question the disregard of creative writers for style guides despite the many advantages of committing to a style guide. In my view, creative writers have not “eschewed” style guides as Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024) said (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41). Nevertheless, creative writers have instead refused to document style guides as they believe that every creative or good writer must naturally be inclined to follow a standard English writing style, which presupposes that their style guide is in their memory. I also think that creative writers follow their imaginations to create and do not want to be tied down by a particular writing style as they may not know where their work will be published at conception. Hence, they are better off not to document or write down a specific style guide as it may lead to having so many documents. However, creative writers should be dynamic enough to quickly adapt to a client’s style guide at any point in time, just as freelancers do.

7) THE CHICAGO MANUAL STYLE

The Chicago Style of Writing is used in formatting books, theses, dissertations and term papers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 44). Aside from the Chicago style of Writing, there are several other writing styles, including the American Psychological Association (APA), the Modern Language Association (MLA), and the Harvard style. Until this course, I never knew that the Chicago Style of Writing is also referred to as the Turabian style of writing; however, upon further reading of the course materials, I have found that the CMS is meant for book publishing while The Turabian style is used for term papers, dissertations, research papers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 51). This underscores why Euclid University subscribes to the Turabian writing style for students.

The Turabian style of writing gives instructions on the use of abbreviations, the use of capital letters. I did not know that abbreviations (e.g., i.e., etc.) must always be used in parentheses as a rule under the Chicago writing style. This point is well noted and will be applied in all my papers (e.g., Response Paper 1).

8) COMMON LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Seeing the heading “Common Latin Abbreviations and Expressions in the Period One (1) course pack aroused my interest and set me wondering about its importance in essay writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 59–60). However, I uncovered in the course content, to my surprise, I have unknowingly been using standard abbreviations (e.g., A.M, cf, e.g., c.v, et al., i.e.) and expressions (e.g., pro bono, per capita, in situ, et cetera, viva).

9) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it has been an interesting starting point for me. It has dawned on me that as a Ph.D. student, I must learn to unlearn and relearn. This ACA-401D period one (1) course pack has helped me identify some knowledge gaps I had in writing academic papers regarding the use of punctuation, referencing and citations, and writing styles that go into technical writing. The tutorial video by Gulma (2024) also touched on salient points about using the template in Microsoft Word, among others. Overall, Period 1 content has prepared me for the subsequent periods in academic writing and other courses I will take on my Ph.D. journey.

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